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FLUORESCENT EUTECTOGELS FOR THE DETECTION OF PFAS IN WATER

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Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are persistent contaminants detected in aquatic environments and linked to adverse health and ecological impacts.¹ Their analysis typically requires sophisticated chromatographic and mass-spectrometric methods, underscoring the need for simpler and faster detection strategies.

We report a fluorescent sensing platform based on eutectogels containing carbon dots (CDs) for PFAS detection in water. CDs were synthesized via a straightforward procedure and characterized by NMR, FTIR, DSC, TGA, and X-ray diffraction, confirming nanoscale carbonaceous structures with fluorescence-active functionalities.² Different CDs loadings were incorporated into polymer eutectogels.^{3,4} Based on structural, thermal, and morphological characterization, including SEM, water uptake, and rheological measurements, the eutectogel containing 0.25 wt% CDs was identified as exhibiting optimal structural integrity and mechanical performance.

Under UV irradiation, the eutectogels exhibit stable fluorescence. Furthermore, exposure to PFBS and PFOA induces clear fluorescence changes, demonstrating the material's responsiveness, although without specific compound selectivity. Overall, this work highlights CD-eutectogel hybrid materials as a simple, rapid, and visually interpretable sensing platform, offering a promising route for practical and accessible screening of PFAS contamination in water.

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References

1. E. M. Sunderland, X. C. Hu, C. Dassuncao, A. K. Tokranov, C. C. Wagner, J. G. Allen, *J. Exposure Sci. Environ. Epidemiol.*, 2019, 29, 131–147.
2. Y. Wang, A. Hu, *J. Mater. Chem. C*, 2014, 2, 6921–6939.
3. L. C. Tomé, D. Mecerreyes, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2020, 124, 8465–8478.
4. E. Gabirondo, J. M. M. Araújo, A. B. Pereira, L. C. Tomé, *ChemSusChem*, 2025, 18, e202500307.